

Advances in theory of physical geomorphometry

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Abstract— The development of the physical-geomorphometric (PG) theory is necessary for the development of its methods and applications. The new system of basic 2D PG quantities including both the derivatives (up to changes of curvatures) and dispersions (roughness) in their mutual relationships is the first innovation of the concept presented. Further, the principles of construction of PG indices from these basic quantities are outlined. A new concept of 3D physical geomorphometry of caves is also introduced, linked to the previously defined concept of endogenous and exogenous work. Finally, the role of DEM generalization and its essential properties needed for physically based segmentations are presented.

I. INTRODUCTION

Physical geomorphometry has been defined in [1] and [2] as a specific subfield of geomorphometry that examines the form of the land surface in relation to the principles, procedures, and concepts of physics, such as dimensions, energy, work, force, thermodynamics, and equilibria. As part of the project "Physical Geomorphometry for Physical Geographical Research", we have been developing the theoretical concept, methodology and practical applications of physical geomorphometry since mid-2023. Significant advances in the methodology and applications are presented in separate contributions, here we focus on the theoretical development of the concept.

II. SYSTEM OF PHYSICAL-GEOMORPHOMETRIC QUANTITIES

The gravity potential of unit volume of material obtained by the uplift $\Delta z = 1m$ is the unit Local Geomorphometric Energy (LGE_u). In [2], we have documented that the parts of LGE_u applicable to specific geomorphic processes are defined by the first and second derivatives of altitude (slope sine and various curvatures). In [1], we presented a system, which in addition to these local energies, also include the regional energies/works defined in [3] and [4].

Now we extend this system by changes of curvatures and of the energetic significance of different roughness quantities (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. System of PG quantities, defined by heights: z (a.s.l.), z_{rel} (above local basis of erosion); slope (S); curvatures: k_{mean} (mean), k_d (difference), $(\tau_{\tau})_c$ (twisting – contour torsion), $(k_n)_s$ (profile – normal slope line), $(k_n)_c$ (plan/tangential – normal contour), k_c (Casorati); changes of curvatures: $(k_n)_{ss}$ (slope line change of normal slope line c.), $(k_n)_{cs}$ (slope line change of normal contour c.), $(k_n)_{cc}$ (contour change of normal contour c.); dispersions of the above in moving window: Δ (range), MAD (mean absolute deviation). Arrows express the hierarchy (subordination) of quantities. Hitherto unpublished energies are framed in dashes.

The changes in curvature express the changes in the acceleration and concentration energies. The deviations of heights express the ExW that still needs to be done (without considering external influence) in order to achieve a static equilibrium (surface leveled to z_{mean}). The deviations of the derivatives of the heights can then be interpreted as energy, the removal of which achieves the equilibrium state of the energies resulting from the derivatives.

Two basic dichotomies are contained in this system: division into *Pointwise* and *Areal energy* and *Total* and *Available* energy.

Pointwise energies (in red in Fig. 1) are energies specific to each individual point of the land surface. They are linked with position of the point above global or local basis of erosion (absolute height z and relative height z_{rel}) and *derivatives of height*. The former include fundamental global and regional geomorphic energy (GGE and RGE) given by heights. In accordance with [5] height derivatives are local point-based geomorphometric variables expressing the behavior (variation) of a surface in the infinitesimal vicinity of a point. Physically, they represent a hierarchy of changes in LGE_u acting at a given point [2].

Areal energies (in violet in Fig. 1) express the energy of the area (window) from which they are calculated. They may represent central tendencies, extremes or dispersion measures of pointwise energies resulting from heights and their derivatives. Maxima and means of altitude were used to define endogenous and exogenous work in [3] and height range was used to define the relief brake force. The whole set of other areal energies can be defined using roughness measures traditionally expressed mainly by standard deviations. However, a more straightforward energetic interpretation is provided by the mean absolute deviation (MAD) used in Fig. 1. In line with [2] local area-based variables can represent the local energies if they are calculated from the smallest possible window, or regional energies if the size of the window corresponds to the wavelength of the land surface (topographic grain TG). Therefore, if areal energies are to have a specific regional character, should be computed from window $\geq TG$.

Total energies (shades of orange with a thick frame in Fig. 1) represent the total gravitational potential of pointwise and areal characteristics of heights, which can also be interpreted as the entire measurable energy spent on long-term geomorphic work that formed land surface. They are multiples of LGE_u reaching values $\leq z_{max} \cdot LGE_u$. They have their own hierarchy ($GGE \geq RGE$ and $EnW \geq LGE \geq ExW \geq Full PoExW \geq Residual PoExW$) which results from the statistical relationships between the maximum, mean, range and deviation of z and z_{rel} , but also from their geomorphological (PG) interpretation. Normally, the local base of erosion cannot be below sea level, therefore GGE is the superior energy and the RGE is the subordinate energy (it is only a part of GGE). Likewise, ExW , which only eliminates EnW , cannot exceed its value, and thus EnW is superior and ExW is subordinate, etc.

Available energies (with a thin frame in Fig. 1) can also be both, pointwise and areal. However, compared to the total

energies, they are only a fraction of LGE_u , reaching values $\leq LGE_u$. They express parts of LGE_u that are available for certain current geomorphic processes (morphodynamics). They are therefore usually significantly smaller than total energies reflecting long-term development (morphogenesis). Their hierarchy (superiority and subordination) again results from both the mathematical essence and the PG interpretation. The higher derivatives of heights are (for physical reasons) smaller than the lower derivatives, so the slope represents more energy than curvatures and those greater than curvature changes. This hierarchy of pointwise energies is also transferred to the areal available energies.

III. DEFINING PHYSICAL-GEOMORPHOMETRIC INDICES

Assigning a clear and compatible physical meaning to basic geomorphometric variables opens space for a new (physical) interpretation and improvement of topographic indices derived from them, as well as the definition of new indices. An example given in [2] is the energy interpretation of the popular Index of Connectivity ([6]) as the sum of upstream regional concentration energy and downstream mass flow energy. Similarly, the χ -index [7] can be interpreted as the ratio of overall regional energy to regional concentration energy, which tends to be constant for equilibrium longitudinal river profiles under conditions of geological homogeneity. The importance of PG insight into the issue lies not only in a clearer interpretation, but also in the possible modification (optimization) of such indices. In the case of the χ -index, it can be, for example, the substitution of the 2D projected catchment area (which by default enters its calculation) with a 3D area considering the distribution of slopes in it.

The construction of completely new PG indices is another significant possibility (see e.g. [2], [3], [4]). In general, these indices can be defined as the ratio, difference or sum of different types of geomorphic energies. The informative value of each such index is substantial. For example, if we compare energies in a hierarchical relationship, it is important to realize that the uniform spatial distribution of superior energies is usually associated with some kind of equilibrium, and hierarchically subordinate energies are generally responsible for instability in the geosystem. An increase in the proportion of subordinate energy thus signals an imbalance of the system, the type of which depends on the nature of the subordinate energy. Currently, we are focused on deriving a set of PG indices to define the PG signature of various genetic landform types [8]. The traditional concept of geometric signature [9] based on descriptive statistics / geomorphometry is now widely applied in modern segmentation and classification methods based on artificial intelligence (machine learning). In addition to its indisputable advantages (they can well replicate known forms), its main shortcoming is its black box approach obscuring the physical reasons for why some variables are most

important – e.g. [10]). The clear physical interpretation of the PG signature components makes this concept a white box system.

IV. 3D CAVE PHYSICAL GEOMORPHOMETRY

We have defined the concept of unit total cave work CW (concerning the change of gravitational potential of $1m^3$ of material) using the ratio of V_{cave} (volume of the cave) and A_{cave} (area of the cave map projection – see Fig. 2a):

$$CW = (1m^3) \cdot \frac{V_{cave}}{A_{cave}} \cdot \rho \cdot g \quad (1)$$

The CW is defined in this way as a specific subsurface variant of exogenous work (ExW). The ExW is defined in [3] by the difference in maximum and mean height as the portion of past endogenous work (EnW) eliminated by exogenous processes. By analogy, CW will present the elimination of EnW , which, however, has not yet manifested itself at surface altitudes (theoretically, it would be reflected in them when the cave ceiling collapses). This CW concept allows the whole 3D physical geomorphometry of caves to link directly with the surface 2D geomorphometry system (Fig. 1) and to define other PG characteristics of caves using transverse profiles through their passages (Fig. 2b).

Relations in Fig. 2 are derived from relation (1). The CW_{tp} is derived for a horizontal circular passage, with slope of center line $\beta = 0$. In a more general case ($\beta \neq 0$), equation takes the form:

$$CW_{tp} = (1m^3) \cdot \frac{A_p(.1m)}{2r_p(.1m) \cdot \cos\beta + A_p \cdot \sin\beta} \cdot \rho \cdot g \quad (2)$$

Figure 2. Derivation of cave physical geomorphometry: **A** Total cave work given by relation (1); **B.** Cave profiles works. For more explanation see the text.

The equation for CW_{ac} suggests that the roughness of the 3D cave surface can also be physically interpreted. And it does not have to be only in the sense of total (genetic) categories, but also dynamically as a cave barrier effect.

V. LANDFORM HIERARCHY, GENERALIZATION AND SEGMENTATION

Mild generalization (smoothing) is commonly used to eliminate DEM errors. This is important for the calculation of curvatures and changes of curvatures, where with the size of the DEM errors, the calculation error increases exponentially.

The purpose of major generalization (filtering) is to remove existing smaller forms for easier analysis of superior larger forms. Just as we can efficiently capture and then analyze individual wavelengths of electromagnetic radiation using specialized telescopes, targeted generalization of DEM is a prerequisite for effective PG analysis. In this case, the land surface can be perceived (according to information theory) as a 2D nonstationary signal consisting of multiresolution components and generalization is a filtering of original signal [11].

The profiles on Fig. 3 schematically depict not only the forms of various hierarchical levels, but (in accordance with Fig. 1) they can also be perceived as an expression of the spatial distribution of geomorphic energies. The most important attributes of this signal are wavelength (topographic grain) and amplitude. Generalization (filtering) should preserve them as best as possible until they are not separated from the signal. The most common simple generalization methods are not capable of this. Polygonal simplification method using Quadric Error Metrics is much better, but it limits the subsequent calculation of higher derivatives [14].

Figure 3. Swath profile across the Western Carpathians (according [12]) as a non-stationary signal of multi-resolution components (according [11]). The signal changes the most at the boundaries of the basic geological units, but it is also specific for each smaller morphostructural unit (on the right, according [13]). S – the smoothest component of the signal (form of highest hierarchic level), $D1$ - $D5$ – more detailed components (incorporating increasingly smaller forms).

We need generalization method that allows subsequent calculation of all variables and will keep the signal (forms of a given hierarchical level) as clear as possible until it is deleted. This is important for physically based elementary segmentation [2] – a part of discrete geomorphometry [15], that looks for internally homogeneous objects separated by discrete boundaries. Therefore, the generalization method should not smooth the edges, but rather accentuate and, ideally, also increases the homogeneity of PG variables between edges, as our new method does [16].

Choosing the generalization level most suitable for segmentation is a specific problem. Maximizing the concentration of changes of curvatures values around zero (K_0 index) seems to be a good criterion ([2], [8], [14]), however, so far it has only been applied in small areas and has not been confronted with modern multiscale analysis based on information theory such as Wavelet Transform (WT) and Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD). As the information signal changes in different morphostructural units (Fig. 3), the most appropriate level of generalization can also change. The same applies to the calculation of the wavelength (topographic grain), which is crucial for the calculation of regional PG variables (Fig. 1). The development of the PG quantities system and the PG indices derived from them allows for the improvement of segmentation algorithms and geomorphological interpretation of segmentation results. It seems appropriate to reconsider the calculation of inputs to morphostructural segmentation [4] and look for an increasingly optimal expression of PG signature relief forms [2].

VI. CONCLUSIONS

All analyzed aspects of physical geomorphometry are interconnected and important for the development of its methods. Improving of the system of PG quantities gives new interpretative views on the quantities themselves, but also allows us to see their combinations in traditional geomorphometric indices, improve them or create new PG indices. This enables to improve the methods of physically-based segmentation and their use within digital geomorphological mapping. The proposed concept of cave work connects 2D and 3D PG geomorphometry and outlines the potential of studying the roughness of cave surfaces. The theoretically defined requirements for the DEM generalization in the context of physical geomorphometry are crucial for the development and application of a suitable generalization method and adaptation of PG segmentation algorithms in larger areas. All this points to the need to develop methods of physical geomorphometry in mutual interaction, within its synthetic theoretical concept.

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